

How NASA uses OPeNDAP

Summary

NASA is a global leader in monitoring the Earth's environment and climate. Their satellites collect data used to track environmental change, record imagery of the Earth, support weather forecasting, among other uses. NASA's monitoring efforts have resulted in over 100 PB of Earth observation data that they store and manage. All of these data are made available for free to the general public, who use them to track air quality, manage water and land resources, and make decisions about predicted natural disasters. To help accomplish these data management goals, NASA leverages OPeNDAP's streaming data access technology.

NASA's goals

NASA began collecting Earth observation data in 1972 with the launch of the Landsat 1 satellite. Over the next few decades, NASA's growing data were stored on-site at data centers located in different places across the US. With each data center focusing on a specific Earth science discipline, such as atmospheric science or snow and ice, these data centers also manage and distribute data to users.

In 2019, NASA began partnering with Amazon Web Services (AWS) to migrate their data to the cloud, building a system known as [Earthdata Cloud](#). Such a migration was intended to:

- **Improve access to data** by reducing the need to download data to local machines.
- **Allow faster and more efficient data processing**, including supporting high-performance computing for analyzing large datasets in near-real time.
- **Allow for scalability** as NASA's earth science data continues to grow by several terabytes (TB) per day.
- **Be more cost-effective** by reducing the need for hardware maintenance, data duplication, and overall cost of long-term storage.
- **Enhance collaboration** by having one central location for datasets that all users—no matter their discipline—can use.

Working with OPeNDAP

To achieve some of their data management goals, NASA has been leveraging OPeNDAP's technology and expertise for over ten years. OPeNDAP's data streaming services help make access to NASA's data faster, more efficient, and less expensive.

OPeNDAP's state-of-the-art technology provides NASA's Earthdata users with:

- **Remote Cloud data access**
- **Data subsetting** so a user can request and stream only the data they want from a much larger dataset.
- **Metadata mapping technology** to make remote data access and subsetting fast and precise. "Lazy metadata-loading" helps users save time by requesting the most essential metadata, while deferring access to more detailed information.
- **Streamlined user workflows** that allow people to use any analysis language (Python, R), tool (ArcGIS), and data format (HDF4/5) to access and analyze data.
- **Single sign-on** so data users can access data that require authentication (often required amongst NASA datasets) without having to log-in multiple times.
- **Scalable Deployments** with a resting state of 16 systems handling 50k requests/min, scaling to over 100 systems handling >1M requests/min.
- **Scalable Tiered Caching** improves response times.

NASA represents a super-charged data provider that uses OPeNDAP's technologies. These same data management challenges are common across any sector that works with large volumes of data, and especially legacy data that can accumulate over decades.

About OPeNDAP

OPeNDAP is a 501(c)3 not-for-profit corporation and the developer of a suite of open source software tools, including the Hyrax data server and DMR++. OPeNDAP's software facilitates efficient remote data exchange by allowing users to stream subsets of data from large datasets and use data without needing to download and reformat data. OPeNDAP's state-of-the-art technology provides fast and convenient access to data—especially for data stored in the cloud, helping data providers and data users save time and money. Most well-known for their long-time support of NASA's Earth science data system, OPeNDAP's technology is applicable to any data-intensive domain or sector.

To learn more about OPeNDAP, please reach out to us at support@opendap.org.